

For high tech industry to find physical characteristics of thin clad layer of Stellite-6 (Cobalt Base Alloys) deposited by laser cladding

Muhammad Usman^{1*}, Tauqeer Ahmad², Ahmad aqrab ul¹, Musheer Ahmad²,
Muhammad Umair¹

¹Peter the Great St. Petersburg Polytechnic University, Saint Petersburg, Russia

²The Government College University, Lahore, Pakistan

Abstract: This research was aimed at the development of production methods and tools needed to achieve a high degree of reliability and integrity of laser clad components manufactured at high production rate. These targets can be realized by understanding the laser/materials interactions during laser cladding. A thin surface layer of cobalt-based alloys (Stellite-6) was deposited on mild steel substrates by a coaxial laser cladding process. This process could produce a thin surface layer of less than 0.71 mm with low energy input. Laser-clad Stellite-6 specimens exhibited refined dendritic microstructure. There are interdendritic eutectics which consist of either small-scale carbides or compounds which are intermetallic and randomly distributed in a cobalt-rich solid solution, unlike the lamellar structure as observed in conventional weld overlays. The hardness values of the laser-clad layers were generally higher than those of conventional welding deposits owing to the refined effect. The wear and corrosion resistance of S-6 specimens were considerably better. Experimental results indicated that wear and corrosion characteristics of the Stellite-6 specimen were excellent; however, Proper powder feed rate and preheating were required to avoid cracking in the laser cladding process. Moreover, several approaches and steps were taken to identify the optimal process conditions to produce satisfactory clad layers with desired hardness and low residual stresses to avoid defects and Cracking and distortion.

Keywords: Laser Cladding, Microstructure Characteristics, Micro Hardness, Corrosion Resistance, Wear Resistance

*Corresponding Author:

Accepted: 21 December, 2022; **Published:** 25 December, 2022

How to cite this article: Muhammad Usman, Tauqeer Ahmad, Ahmad aqrab ul, Musheer Ahmad, Muhammad Umair (2022). For high tech industry to find physical characteristics of thin clad layer of Stellite-6 (Cobalt Base Alloys) deposited by laser cladding. North American Academic Research, 5(12), 64-77. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7480360>

Conflicts of Interest: There are no conflicts to declare.

Publisher's Note: NAAR stays neutral about jurisdictional claims in published maps/image and institutional affiliations.

Copyright: ©2022 by the authors. Author(s) are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in this manuscript submitted for possible open access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Introduction

Cobalt-based alloys are widely used in wear-related applications because of their inherent high-strength, corrosion resistance, and retained hardness over a wide temperature range [1]. The hardness of cobalt-based alloys is derived generally from the high hardness of carbides or intermetallic compounds in the cobalt-rich solid solution. The

abrasion resistance of these alloys is dependent on the volume fraction, size, and morphology of these hard particles [2,3]. The corrosion resistance of cobalt-based alloys is generally good in many environments. Nevertheless, the corrosion resistance in terms of corrosion rate of a given alloy depends on type, concentration, and temperature of the acidic solution [1,4]. The Stellite alloys are wear-resistant cobalt-based alloys, in which Stellite-6 is the most versatile material and well-suited for a wide range of hard facing applications [4,5]. Micro structurally, the wear resistance of Stellite-6 alloy is attributed to the highness of M₇C₃ carbides at interdendritic regions in both as-cast and as-welded conditions [1]. A detailed discussion of microstructural features and mechanical properties of Stellite-6 laser coatings has been presented elsewhere [6]. Conversely, Other cobalt alloys consist of a hard Laves phase in a softer matrix of eutectic or solid solution, which are particularly useful for lubricated wear situations [7,8]. For instant cobalt alloys (Tribaloy T-900) was developed for improved crack resistance in the Tribaloy family by increasing the Ni content significantly and reducing Mo of Tribaloy T-800 alloy [9]. Laser cladding is an advanced coating technology which has the advantage of depositing a thin surface coating on the selected area of metal substrates with controlled thickness. It is characterized by a short interaction time of the high energy density beam with the powder and the substrate. As a result, the process has a low energy input and causes less distortion of the component than conventional welding methods. Steen [10] and Bruck [11] gave good overviews on the laser surface processes. Process of laser cladding which is coaxial, powder of metal is injected with a nozzle. Laser energy is absorbed in the powder and it becomes partly melt substrate prior it reaches the substrate. Part of the laser energy is also absorbed by the substrate to cause melting in surface, which forms an impregnable metallurgical adhesion between substrate and the clad stratum. Laser cladding can be used not only in the new production but also in the restoration of worn components. Laser-clad layers with defect free and low dilution have been reported [12,13]. The purpose of this study was focused on the surface properties of laser clad Stellite-6 specimens. Surface properties such as wear and corrosion behavior of various laser-clad specimens were determined by abrasive wear and corrosion resistant tests, respectively. In addition, micro structural examinations and micro hardness profiles were carried out on laser-clad specimens.

2. Materials and Experiments

Following Materials are used to perform this work:

2.1 Stellite-6

2.2 Mild steel

Stellite cobalt base alloys consist of complex carbides in an alloy matrix. They are resistant to wear, galling and corrosion and retain these properties at high temperatures. Their uncommon wear resistance is expected for the most part to the special inalienable attributes of the hard carbide stage scattered in a CoCr combination network.

Stellite-6 is the most widely used of the wear resistant cobalt based alloys and exhibits good all-round performance It is viewed as the business standard for broadly useful wear resistance applications, has amazing imperviousness to many types of mechanical and compound debasement over a wide temperature run, and holds a sensible level of hardness up to 500°C (930°F). It also has good resistance to impact and cavitation erosion. Satellite 6 is most preferably conformed to diverse of hard facing processes and can be turned with carbide tooling. Examples include valve seats and gates; pump shafts and bearings, erosion shields and rolling couples. It is often used self-mated. Mellow steel contains around 0.05–0.25% carbon making it moldable and malleable. Mellow steel has a generally low rigidity, however it is shoddy and simple to shape; surface hardness can be expanded through carburizing. It is regularly utilized when substantial amounts of steel are required, for instance as basic steel.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Microstructure characterization

Below figures shows a typical metallography displaying the cross-section of laser-clad layers on a mild steel substrate in which the overlapping of successive trucks is clearly identifiable. The clad layer is defect-free of approximately 0.4

mm thick and forms an excellent metallurgical bond with the substrate. During the coaxial laser cladding process, the power attenuation by Stellite-6 powder was about 56% as measured by a power meter under experimental conditions. The power attenuation could be obtained from the ratio of power reading with powder stream (which was blown away by compressed air at the same stand-off distance as in the laser cladding process) to that without powder stream. The effect of power attenuation would reduce the energy absorbed by the substrate and also minimize the dilution between the clad layer and the substrate.

Moreover in Figure 1, we can see that clad power is not melt properly and slightly uneven dilution.

Figure 1: Microscopic view (cross-section and longitudinal) of laser clad specimen at power 300/400

In this Figure 2 we can see that there is an uneven and in some area has angled dilution of powder.

Figure 2: Microscopic view (cross-section and longitudinal) of laser clad specimen at power 450/550 Nevertheless as we increase the laser power and powder feed rate we find better and even dilution and even clad layer as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Microscopic view (cross-section and longitudinal) of laser clad specimen at power 600/700

From the below Figures, we can see that clad powder is not properly melt and mixed up as compare if we increase power of laser and feed rate of powder the clad powder properly melt and mixed and give good grain size [14].

Figure 4: Microscopic view (cross-section and longitudinal) of laser clad layer at power 450/550

Figure 5: Microscopic view (cross-section and longitudinal) of laser clad layer at power 600/700

3.2 Micro hardness

Figure gave the hardness profile of laser-clad specimens, in which the average hardness of Stelite-6 specimens within the top 0.71 mm coating layers is 529.2, 498.8, and 523.6 Hv, respectively. Clearly, the Stelite-6 specimen-3 has the highest hardness among various specimens being tested, while the hardness of the S-6 specimen-2 is about the same as that of the Stelite-6 specimen-1. Figure 6 also shows that the hardness of clad layers in all specimens on all region is much higher than the substrate and the hardness decreases slightly near the fusion boundary, indicating the existence of a narrow region of dilution in specimens, as hardness in Transition phase, heat effected zone phase and base metal are 262.1, 338.1 and 173.4 respectively.

Table 1: Micro hardness at different points

Marked Points		Middle Point	Top Point	Down Point
Sample 1	Longitunal	528.1	511.6	458.1
	Cross-sectional	490.1	472.5	506.6

Sample 2	Longitunal	496.1	502.3	614.6
	Cross-sectional	531.2	494.5	536.5
Sample 3	Longitunal	482.3	480.6	517.3
	Cross-sectional	529.2	498.8	523.6

Transition phases of the different materials

Transition phase hardness	TPH	262.1
Heat Affected zone hardness	HAZH	338.1
Base material hardness	BMH	173.4

Figure 6: Graphical Representation of Micro hardness at different points

3.3 Corrosion Resistance

Potentiodynamic curves of three laser-clad specimens exposed to 0.1 M and 0.5 M HCl solutions at room temperature are displayed in Fig. 9(a) and (b), respectively. It can be seen that no active-to-passive transition peaks form S-6 and

T-900 specimens, indicating that the clad layers of these specimens were passivated spontaneously in these solutions. The corrosion potential of T-900 specimen's is 274 mV and 110 mV in 0.1 M and 0.5 M HCl solutions, respectively. These values are nobler than the corrosion potential of S-6 specimens in the solution of concern, i.e. 384 mV in 0.1 M HCl and 351 mV in 0.5 M HCl

Figure 7: Potentiodynamic curves of three laser-clad specimens in (a) 0.1 M and (b) 0.5 M HCl solutions of at room temperature solutions.

It is noted that the 410 SS specimen does not reveal an active-to-passive transition but exhibits a rapid increase in current density with increasing potential in both 0.1 M and 0.5 M HCl solutions. The corrosion potential of the 410 SS specimen in these solutions is more active than that of cobalt-based alloy specimens. The corrosion current density (I_{corr}) is determined by the Tafel extrapolation method [15] from potentiodynamic curves in Fig. 7. The linear portion of the anodic or cathodic polarization potential vs. log (current) plot is extrapolated to intersect the potential line. The value of either the anodic or the cathodic current at the intersection is I_{corr} in the Tafel plot. Although a fully linear portion of the curve is not necessary to calculate I_{corr} by the associated software of the potentiostatic, the better accuracy of I_{corr} requires the longer linear region in the Tafel plot. The corrosion rate (Am/year) is related to I_{corr} by the equation (Faraday's law) with the assumption of n (number of electrons taking part in the reaction) equals to.

$$\text{Corrosion rate}(\mu\text{m}/\text{year}) = \frac{3.27 \left(I_{\text{corr}}, \mu\text{A}/\text{cm}^2 \right) \left(\text{Equivalent weight, g} \right)}{\left(\text{Density, g}/\text{cm}^3 \right)}$$

It is worthwhile to mention that the above equation is only valid in cases of uniform corrosion and can be used to index the relative corrosion resistance of metals in a specific environment. Table 2 lists the corrosion current density (I_{corr}) and the corrosion rate (Am/year) of laser-clad specimens in HCl solutions.

Table 2: Corrosion rate of various laser-clad specimens exposed in HCl solutions

Solution	Specimen	I _{corr} (AA/cm ²)	Corrosion rate (Am/y)a
0.1 M HCl at 25 -C	S-6	4.153	45
	T-900	1.327	15
	410 SS	44.91	519
0.5 M HCl at 25 -C	S-6	48.01	516
	T-900	2.049	23
	410 SS	915.5	10580

1 Am/year; 0.04 mpy (milli-inches per year).

The calculated equivalent weight and the associated density of S-6, T-900, and 410 SS specimens are 27.75g/8.44 g/cm³, 30.42 g/8.85 g/cm³, and 27.39 g/7.75 g/cm³, respectively. As can be seen in Table 2, the corrosion rate of T-900 specimens in either 0.1 M HCl (15 Am/year) or 0.5 M HCl (23 Am/year) is the lowest among specimens being tested. The T-900 specimen has a corrosion rate about 33% of the S-6 specimen in 0.1 M HCl, but it becomes less than 5% of the S-6 specimen in 0.5 M HCl solution. The I_{corr} of the 410 SS specimen is approximately 45 AA/cm² in 0.1 M HCl and raises to 916 AA/cm² in 0.5 M HCl solutions. These values are much higher than the I_{corr} values of cobalt based alloy specimens in respective solutions. The corrosion rate of the 410 SS specimen is about 519 Am/year in 0.1 M HCl and reaches an extremely high level of 10,580 Am/year in 0.5 M HCl solution.

Figure 8: Corrosion Resistance (Potentiodynamic curves) of Stellite-6 laser-clad specimens in (a) and (b) 3.5% M NaCl solutions of at room temperature.

As shown in Figure 8, we found following prospects:

1. The more positive final OC potential (last point in E vs time) shows more noble behavior of material
2. The higher point where current density started rapidly increase shows better corrosion resistance.

The superior corrosion resistance of cobalt-based alloy specimens, particularly Tribaloy T-900, when compared to the corrosion resistance of the 410 SS specimen in hydrochloric acid solution has been demonstrated. It has been reported that the corrosion resistance of Stellite alloys is generally good in many acids but poor in hydrochloric acid [16]. The potentiodynamic behavior of various laser-clad specimens in hydrochloric acid solution could be used to index their relative corrosion resistance in a hostile environment. From the results discussed above, the advantages of laser coating cobalt-based alloys on metal components are evident, not only to improve the wear resistance but also to enhance corrosion protection. However, the selection of cladding materials for corrosion protection is also dependent on the environment in a particular application.

3.4 Wear Resistance

The wear loss of various laser-clad specimens against sliding distance in wear tests is shown in Figure 9. The wear loss increases in the order through the T-900, S-6, and 410 SS specimens. For instance, the wear loss of the T-900 specimen after sliding distance of 1000 meters is 11 mg, which is noticeably less than 17 mg and 61 mg of S-6 and 410 SS specimens, respectively. Apparently, Laves intermetallic in the T-900 specimen contributes appreciably to the wear resistance. The superior wear resistance of cobalt based alloys over an iron-based alloy at the similar hardness level is evident. It is noted that the wear rate, slope of the wear curves in Figure 9, is nearly constant for S-6 and T-900 specimens. However, the wear rate of the 410 SS specimen is considerably higher in the initial 300 m than the last 700 m of sliding distance, i.e. an obvious change in slope of the wear curve occurs at approximately 300 m. This could be attributed to the greater extent of (1) reduction in the cutting efficiency of the abrasive particles through capping and clogging [17,18] and (2) to working hardening in the subsurface region [19].

Figure 4.10 shows the worn surfaces of laser-clad specimens after wear tests. The worn surfaces of S-6 and T-900 specimens (Figure 10 (a) and (b)) appear to be similar, showing the effect of microploughing and grooving on specimens by hard SiC particles during abrasive wear. However, the shallower grooves are observed on the worn surface of the T-900 specimen. In contrast, the 410 SS specimen (Figure 10 (c)) reveals extensive ploughing together with oxidational wear on the worn surface. In addition, fins are also observed at edges of the groove and they are eventually to break off, resulting in a higher wear loss of the 410 SS specimen.

Figure 9: Wear losses as a function of sliding distance for laser-clad specimens.

It should be mentioned that the wear resistance is not only dependent on the cladding hardness and the hardness of Stellite-6 coatings is strongly dependent on solidification microstructures [20]. The wear resistance is also a function of some other factors such as the modulus of elasticity, microstructure including the size and distribution of hard particles in the alloy, size and hardness of abrasive particles, sliding distance, and applied load [21]. For example, the hardness of Satellite 6 overlays deposited by PTA process is 450 Hv, which is considerably less than 530 Hv of laser-clad S-6 specimens. The same trend has been observed for the T-900 PTA weld deposit [22]. The low hardness of PTA overlays is attributed to the presence of coarse solidification structures as discussed previously.

However, the wear loss of the PTA overlay after 1000 m sliding distance is 10 mg, which is similar to that of T-900 but less than 17 mg of the S-6 specimen. Apparently, the fine carbides associated with S-6 specimens are readily pulled out rather than worn down in the abrasive wear tests. This is consistent with the report that the abrasive resistance of Satellite alloys is improved as the carbide size increases [23].

Figure 10: SEM photographs showing the worn surfaces of (a) S-6, (b) T-900, and (c) 410 SS specimens after wear tests.

On the other hand, alloys used for abrasive protection may not be suitable for erosion resistant applications because different wear mechanisms are involved. It has been reported that the weld overlay coatings of Satellite 6 (~445 Hv) exhibit relatively poor erosion resistance compared to the erosion resistance of Inconel 625 (~235 Hv) and 316 L stainless steel (~185 Hv) [24]. It can be concluded that a higher hardness of the clad layer does not necessarily guarantee to have better wear performance, since wear resistance, as pointed out by Antony [25], is a system parameter rather a material property. Consequently, most of the successful applications of cladding materials were gained by experiments under specific conditions.

4. Conclusion

1. Surface modification of metal components can be achieved by coaxial laser cladding alloy powders onto the area of interest. This process could produce thin surface layers of less than 0.5 mm with low energy input. It is well suitable for anti-wear/corrosion applications where a thin clad layer and a strong bond to the substrate are required.
2. S-6 and T-900 laser-clad layers exhibited refined dendrites with eutectics at the interdendritic regions. These regions consisted of small carbides or Laves particles randomly distributed in cobalt-rich solid solution, not necessarily in

lamellar form. Laser-clad Satellite 6 layers had the average hardness higher than PTA weld overlays, but did not have better wear performance.

3. The wear resistance of laser-clad layers decreased in order through the T-900, S-6, and 410 SS specimens under experimental conditions. The T-900 specimen had the highest hardness and the lowest wear loss among the tested specimens. In contrast, S-6 and 410 SS specimens had similar hardness but the latter exhibited a significantly higher wear loss in the abrasive wear test.

4. The corrosion resistance of cobalt-based alloy specimens was better than that of the 410 SS specimen in 0.1 M and 0.5 M HCl solutions. The T-900 specimen also had substantially lower corrosion rates than the S-6 specimen in such solutions. The excellent wear and corrosion characteristics of the former were obvious; however, preheating was required to avoid cracking during the laser cladding process. Moreover we face distortion during all process; we need to consider it for further work.

Author Contributions: At first page.

Approval: All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This research received no external funding.

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement: Not applicable

Acknowledgments: Not Mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

References

- [1] K.C. Antony, JOM 35 (2) (1983) 52.
- [2] W.L. Silence, J. Lub. Technol., Trans. ASME 100 (1978) 428.
- [3] K.C. Antony, JOM 35 (2) (1983) 52.
- [4] A.J. Hickl, JOM 32 (3) (1980) 6.
- [5] Cobalt-Base Rods, Electrodes and Wires (W-207), 1982, Stellite Wear Technology, Cabot Corporation, Kokomo, Ind.
- [6] J.L. De Mol Van Otterloo, J.Th.M. de Hosson, Acta Mater. 45 (1997) 1225
- [7] Tribaloy Wear Resistance Intermetallic Materials (W-152), 1980, Wear Technology Division, Cabot Corporation, Kokomo, Ind
- [8] A. Halstead, R.D. Rawlings, J. Mater. Sci. 20 (1985) 1693.
- [9] Tribaloy T-900 Technical Data, Stellite Coating Division, Deloro Stellite Company, Inc., Goshen, Ind., 2002.
- [10] W.M. Steen, in: D. Belforte, M. Levitt (Eds.), The Industrial Laser Annual Handbook, SPIE, vol. 629, PennWell, Tulsa, OK, 1986, pp. 158 – 174
- [11] G.J. Bruck, JOM 39 (2) (1987) 10
- [12] P.J.E. Monson, W.M. Steen, Surf. Eng. 6 (3) (1990) 185
- [13] A. Hirose, K.F. Kobayashi, ISIJ Int. 35 (6) (1995) 757.
- [14] U. Ritter, W. Kahrman, R. Kupfer, and R. Glardon, "Laser coating proven in practice," Sulzer Technical Review, vol. 73, no. 3, pp. 18-20, 1991.
- [15] L.Jianglong, D.Peidao, and S.Gongqi, "Scanning electron microscopy study of laser coating microstructures," Materials Characterization, vol. 33, no. 4, pp. 387–391, 1994.

- [16] L. Xue, A. Therialuit, and M.U. Islam, “Laser consolidation for the manufacturing of complex flextensional transducer shells,” in Proceeding
- [17] L.J. Li and J. Mazumder, “Study of the mechanism of laser cladding processes,” Metallurgical Society of AIME, pp. 35—50, 1985.
- [18] J. Mazumder, “State-of-the-art laser materials processing,” ASME, vol.2, no. 115, pp. 599—630, 1987.
- [19] A. Kar and J. Mazumder, “Effect of cooling rate on solid solubility in laser cladding,” ASME, vol. 3, pp. 237—249, 1987.
- [20] P. Koshy, “Laser cladding techniques for application to wear and corrosion resistant coatings,” Proceedings of SPIE — The International Society for Optical Engineering, vol. 527, pp. 80—85, 1985.
- [21] S.B.Doran, “The laser where flexibility ultimately means economy,” in Production Magazine. 1987.
- [22] L. Shepeleva, B.Medres, W.D. Kaplan, M. Bamberger, and A.Weisheit, “Laser cladding of turbine blades,” Surface and Coatings Technology, vol. 125, no. 1, pp. 45—48, 2000.
- [23] J.L. Koch and J. Mazumder, “Rapid prototyping by laser cladding,” in Laser Material Processing, ICALEO’2003, T.D.Mccay, A. Matsunawa, and H. Hugel, Eds., pp. 556—557. SPIE 2306, 2003.
- [24] M. Murphy, C. Lee, and W.M. Steen, “Studies in rapid prototyping by laser surface cladding,” in Proceeding of ICALEO’1993, pp. 882—891.1993.
- [25] X. Wu, “In situ formation by laser cladding of a tic composite coating with a gradient distribution,” Surface and Coatings Technology, vol.115, no. 2, pp. 111—115, 1999.

